

Response to NIH Request for Information on Maximizing Research Funds by Limiting Allowable Publishing Costs

Submitted by: [Aligning Science Across Parkinson's \(ASAP\)](#)

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RFI: NOT-OD-25-138

We write this letter as a US-based research funding initiative with a record of driving open scientific practices. Aligning Science Across Parkinson's (ASAP) has invested over \$500 million in Parkinson's disease research since 2020, with a small percentage of the budget devoted to article processing charges (APCs). However, these costs add up, and in the past five years, we have collectively spent nearly \$1 million on APCs.

We have thought deeply about the challenges outlined in this Request for Information (RFI) and implemented relevant policies. However, it is only with the critical mass and prominence that the NIH brings, that the community can rapidly transform to comprehensive open access at a fair price.

Below, we outline what we believe to be the fundamental issue underlying unreasonable APCs and present three recommendations.

The Fundamental Problem: Bundled APCs

The current publication system bundles (i) access to a public good (NIH-funded research findings) with (ii) privately organized services (e.g., typesetting, editorial management, curation), under a single APC fee. This bundling distorts the market, where private actors profit from publicly funded research, taxpayers bear unnecessary costs, and access to research outputs is gatekept¹.

APC costs for a single biomedical research publication can range from ~\$1,000 to \$13,000 and ostensibly cover:

1. **Publishing** (making research available to the public, typesetting, internet hosting)
2. **Review** (editorial assessment, researcher-led peer review)
3. **Curation** (selection, promotion of articles)

Until these services and products are unbundled, a fair price is unlikely to emerge. This situation is analogous to a town with a public beach that can only be accessed via restaurants. Market forces drive the restaurants to maximize profit, encouraging them to leverage their gated access to the public beach. In turn, both beachgoers and restaurant-goers pay a premium for offerings they may not be interested in. Likewise, market forces continue to inflate APCs to unreasonable levels. Until the public can access the beach freely (i.e., share and access publicly-funded research findings), we won't know precisely what we're paying for.

Recommendation 1: Require Preprints

Recommendation: NIH should require that research manuscripts be deposited in preprint repositories no later than when submitted to a peer-reviewed outlet. This policy ensures that access to a public good is decoupled from dependence on publishers.

Elaboration: Since 2024, 98% of ASAP-funded manuscripts have been posted as preprints² – on average, 8 months before publication in a journal. ASAP requires preprints³ to be posted to community-recognized repositories, such as bioRxiv or medRxiv, no later than the time a manuscript is submitted to a journal, and with a CC BY license (authors retaining copyright) or CC0 public domain dedication (waiving copyright).

A preprint requirement can work at no cost to the funder and no cost to the researchers while simultaneously fast-tracking the sharing of knowledge. From our experience, it is relatively straightforward to implement this policy at scale and to achieve high levels of compliance through systematic monitoring. Several philanthropic research foundations are advancing a coordinated approach to preprint requirements via the Preprint Policy Framework⁴.

Recommendation 2: Support Preprint Infrastructure

Recommendation: NIH should provide sustained funding for preprint repositories and treat preprints as first-class research outputs in grant evaluation. This approach ensures that preprint repositories are a sustainable long-term solution.

Elaboration: The per article cost for a preprint is often two orders of magnitude less than typical APCs. For example, bioRxiv and medRxiv have published over 350,000 preprints at a cost of approximately \$50-100 per preprint⁵ – as opposed to \$1,000-13,000 for an APC.

These costs are borne by neither the author nor the reader. The largest preprint repositories have relied on philanthropic funding and support from universities⁶. Coordinated and sustained support would be drastically less expensive than having the NIH, other funders, universities, and research institutions continuing to each pay a mix of subscription fees and APCs.

Specific actions could include:

- Expand the scope of the National Library of Medicine's [NIH Preprint Pilot](#)⁷ and make it permanent.
 - Provide sustained funding for PubMed Central, bioRxiv, and medRxiv.
 - Promote peer-reviewed preprints as sufficient for compliance with the NIH Public Access Policy.
 - Treat preprints as first-class outputs in grant applications and grant evaluation.
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Recommendation 3: Focus on value-adds

Recommendation: Regardless of whether there is an APC cap, NIH should continue to support services that improve the quality of scientific research outputs.

Elaboration: A universal cap will not solve some of the underlying issues with APCs. Limiting APCs to \$2,000 promotes mega-journals. These journals often have lower APCs but sometimes [fail to meet basic quality criteria](#)⁸, such as adequate peer review, and [have published AI-generated nonsense](#)⁹. At the same time, the proposed APC cap withdraws support from journals that may use in-house statistical editors, perform systematic checks for compliance with clinical trial regulations, and ensure sharing of data and study protocols – valuable services that cost money. Moreover, commercial journals coasting on historical prestige are likely to evade the price cap. Well-funded investigators will cover the difference from alternative sources while others are left to pay out of pocket.

As in the public beach analogy, providing everyone with a \$20 meal voucher distorts the market, encouraging the fast-food chain to raise their price and for the steakhouse to no longer serve steak, or to no longer serve patrons without additional unrestricted funds. Only after access to public research findings is unbundled from other publishing services can a fair price emerge for each service. If the NIH does decide to implement an APC cap, we urge the NIH to continue its dialogue with the research community, systematically survey for unintended consequences, and engage accordingly.

We're at a crossroads with the opportunity to fundamentally improve how scientific knowledge is shared. By requiring preprints, the NIH can achieve the purpose laid out in the RFI. They can maximize the value of each research grant while providing widespread and immediate access to publicly-funded research findings.

Rather than accepting the existing system's flaws and attempting to regulate around them, NIH can lead transformative change that serves the research community and the American taxpayers who fund it.

References

1. Thibault, R. T., MacPherson, A., Harnad, S., & Raz, A. (2018). The rent's too high: Self-archive for fair online publication costs. arXiv preprint arXiv:1808.06130. <https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.1808.06130>
2. Thibault, R. T., Cobb-Lewis, D. E., Lewis, M. Snyder, D., Blauwendraat, C., Dumanis, S. (2025). A Funder-Led Intervention to Increase the Sharing of Data, Code, Protocols, and Key Laboratory Materials. International Congress on Peer Review and Scientific Publication. <https://peerreviewcongress.org/abstract/a-funder-led-intervention-to-increase-the-sharing-of-data-code-protocols-and-key-laboratory-materials/>
3. The ASAP preprint policy is outlined in the ASAP Open Science Policy Handbook, Section 3.1. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.13769765>
4. <https://asapbio.org/preprint-policy-framework/>
5. In a personal communication, openRxiv informed us that the cost per preprint is \$50-\$100. Publicly available data reveals a similar number: bioRxiv and medRxiv published [62,000 new preprints over the past 12 months](#) on an annual budget of [approximately \\$3 million](#) (i.e., ~\$48/preprint), while they also hosted [over 300,000 additional preprints](#).
 - A search query for bioRxiv *and* medRxiv preprints posted between 01 Sep, 2024 and 31 Aug, 2025 produced 67,204 results. openRxiv informed us that ~62,000 were new preprints and the remainder were revised preprints. https://www.medrxiv.org/search/jcode%3Amedrxiv%7C%7Cbiorxiv%20limit_from%3A2024-09-01%20limit_to%3A2025-08-31%20numresults%3A10%20sort%3Arelevance-rank%20format_result%3Astandard
 - <https://www.science.org/content/article/bid-expand-biorxiv-and-medrxiv-preprint-servers-move-newly-formed-nonprofit>
 - A search query performed on 2025-09-08 for *all* bioRxiv *and* medRxiv preprints ever posted produced 367,712 results (https://www.medrxiv.org/search/jcode%3Amedrxiv%7C%7Cbiorxiv%20limit_from%3A2000-01-01%20limit_to%3A2025-09-07%20numresults%3A10%20sort%3Arelevance-rank%20format_result%3Astandard). Subtracting the preprints from the past 12 months (67,204), leaves just over 300,000.
6. For bioRxiv and medRxiv, see <https://openrxiv.org/about/>. Supporters include: The Chan Zuckerberg Initiative, Cold Spring Harbor Laboratory, the Sergey Brin Family Foundation, The Robert Lourie Foundation, California Institute of Technology, Centre National de la Recherche Scientifique, Fred Hutchinson Cancer Center, Imperial College London, Massachusetts Institute of Technology, Stanford University, The University of Edinburgh, University of Washington, and Vrije Universiteit Amsterdam. For arXiv, see <https://info.arxiv.org/about/funding.html>, which lists Cornell University and the Simons Foundation, among others.
7. <https://pmc.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/about/nihpreprints/>
8. <https://retractionwatch.com/2023/03/21/nearly-20-hindawi-journals-delisted-from-leading-index-amid-concerns-of-papermill-activity/>
9. For example: <https://scienceintegritydigest.com/2024/02/15/the-rat-with-the-big-balls-and-enormous-penis-how-frontiers-published-a-paper-with-botched-ai-generated-images/>. See the Retraction Watch Database (<https://gitlab.com/crossref/retraction-watch-data>) for a complete list of articles retracted for AI-generated content, fake peer review, and paper mill activity.